

Depthmap: Visibility Graph Analysis (VGA) – How-To Guide

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Step 1: Prepare the building plan for Depthmap

Use AutoCAD or any other vector software (e.g., Illustrator) to prepare the plan of your building for Depthmap. It is recommended to simplify the plan and include only the essential layers, such as walls, doors, and furniture. This will make the CAD file lighter and easier to analyze in Depthmap. If you use AutoCAD, ensure that you 'purge' and 'audit' the file to remove any unnecessary layers or blocks. You can switch layers on and off in Depthmap for different analyses, so make sure that essential elements, like 'walls', are always visible. The 'doors' and 'furniture' layers can be turned off for VGA analysis, but they can be switched back on for image export and visualization purposes. Additional layers such as 'voids' or 'glass' may also be used depending on your plan. Along with 'furniture', these layers can remain on for VGA analysis if you are assessing accessibility. For our study, only the 'walls' layer was kept on during VGA and SD analyses to understand visibility. Please refer to the floor plan provided in the 'VGA model' folder as an example.

Once your plan is ready, save it as a dxf file.

Step 2: Import the file in Depthmap

1. Download the latest version of Depthmap from <https://github.com/SpaceGroupUCL/depthmapX/releases>.
2. Install and open the software on your computer.
3. Create a new file from File -> New and import your dxf file from Map -> Import
4. In the Index panel, make sure that you only keep the layer 'walls' on

Step 3: Run Visibility Graph Analysis (VGA)

1. To run a visibility graph analysis, first set a grid by clicking the 'Set Grid' button in the top ribbon. A pop-up window titled 'Set Grid Properties' will appear, prompting you to specify the spacing. We recommend using a 0.6m by 0.6m grid. After setting the grid, press OK. You can toggle the grid on and off by going to View -> Show Grid.

2. With the grid on, you need to fill the area that will be included in the VGA analysis. Click the 'Standard Fill' button in the top ribbon, then click inside the floor plan to designate the area for analysis. If you need to include or exclude additional areas, you must first modify the plan in your CAD software, then repeat the previous steps.

3. Once the area for analysis is filled using the Standard Fill tool, go to Tools -> Visibility -> Make Visibility Graph. A pop-up window titled 'Make Graph Options' will appear; click OK. This will generate the local measure of 'Connectivity'.

- Next, go to Tools -> Visibility -> Run Visibility Graph Analysis to generate the Mean Depth analysis. In the pop-up window titled 'Analysis Options', select 'Calculate Visibility Relationships,' 'Include Global Measures,' and type 'n' in the 'Select Radius' field. Also, check 'Include Local Measures.' Press OK and wait for the analysis to be generated.

- You can view the Mean Depth measure in the Attributes List panel. To change the colour range, click on the measure, then go to Window -> Colour Range. Reverse the blue and red scale to display shallower spaces in warmer colours and deeper spaces in cooler colours.

6. To check the values for Mean Depth, select the measure in the Attributes List panel and go to Attributes -> Column Properties. Here, you can view the maximum, average, minimum, standard deviation, and number of points for the measure. You can also see the values for each point by going to Window -> Table.

Step 4: Run Step Depth Analysis (SD)

1. The Step Depth Analysis is generated from a specific point. To start, select the point from which you want the Step Depth analysis to begin, then go to Tools -> Visibility -> Step Depth and choose Visibility Step. This will generate the Visual Step Depth from the selected point. The results will appear in the Attributes List table, and you can rename the analysis by right-clicking and selecting 'Rename Column.'
2. To perform a Step Depth analysis from additional points, repeat the previous steps with different selections.
3. You can view the Step Depth values by selecting the measure in the Attributes List panel and going to Attributes -> Column Properties.

Step 5: Export image file

To export your file as an image, go to Edit -> Export Screen. Name your export, select your preferred file extension, and save.

Step 6: Save your file

To save your file, go to File -> Save. Choose the folder where you want to save the file and give it an appropriate name.